

1. Free and Informed Consent Form (ICF).

Accept the ICF at this link: <https://forms.gle/gT3iRWsfYJNTqXyX8>

2. Evaluator Information

Area of expertise:

Experience with HCI/accessibility:

Experience with heuristic evaluation:

Total evaluation time:

The evaluation was conducted on:

- Single session
- Multiple sessions

3. User Profile

Person with low vision, who according to Decree No. 3.298/1999, presents visual impairment in the better eye, even with the best optical correction.

4. Usage Scenario

The evaluator should consider the context of a user with low vision accessing the Shopee website to perform common navigation and information-search tasks. During the evaluation, possible difficulties related to visual perception, identification of interactive elements, state changes, navigation continuity, and interface adaptation in situations involving content enlargement and sequential navigation should be observed.

5. Evaluation Procedure

During the evaluation, the participant should:

- perform the proposed tasks;
- apply the heuristic framework during execution;
- record observed evidence;
- classify the severity of each identified problem;
- describe potential impacts for users with low vision;

- provide correction recommendations.

6. Experiment Tasks

Website link: [Shopee](#)

Task 1 - Sequential Navigation

Task description:

Access the Shopee homepage and use exclusively sequential navigation through the interactive interface elements (for example, using the Tab key) until locating the “Highlights for You” section and accessing the third item.

Task 2 - Text Resizing

Task description:

Increase the browser zoom to 200% and navigate through the homepage until locating and accessing the “Books and Magazines” category.

7. Execution Environment

Browser used:

Browser version:

Device:

Operating system:

8. Severity Definition

Level	Description
Low	Minor inconvenience; does not compromise task completion.
Moderate	Makes interaction difficult.
High	Significantly compromises task completion.
Critical	Prevents task execution or user autonomy.

9. Expected Evaluator Data

Describe how the evaluation was conducted:

(e.g., single session or multiple sessions, breaks taken, difficulties encountered during the application).

10. Perception of the Instrument

10.1. Were the heuristics clear?

- Yes
- Partially
- No

10.2. Were the evaluative questions understandable?

- Yes
- Partially
- No

10.3. Were there redundant heuristics?

- Yes
- No

10.4. During the application of the framework, were there any difficulties in interpretation or use?

10.5. Observations:
